

E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality

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Abstract:- The study generally aimed to develop a Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System for Tagudin Municipality that would assist the staff to manage the clients record. Specifically, to determine the current process of ticketing in the municipality of Tagudin, to identify the features that to be integrated in the developed system, and to assess the level of acceptability of the developed system. The researchers utilized the descriptive developmental research design. Rapid Application Model (RAD) was the software model used as basis to develop the system. The researchers conducted interview and floated survey questionnaire. WAMMI survey questionnaire was adopted to evaluate the acceptability of the developed system. Based from the evaluation, the respondents perceived that the E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality is Highly Acceptable.

Keywords:- Assessor Ticketing System; Rapid Application Development; style; styling; WAMMI (key words)

I. INTRODUCTION

The government is one if not the most critical backbone of a functioning society. Its purpose for existing helps us maintain order, and for the government to run correctly, it needs revenues and taxes, which can only be achieved through compelling administration. An effective administration running the government would maintain prosperity and prevent their respective countries from facing crises; examples of these crises are starvation, anarchy, illiteracy, and economic problems. A significant way for the government to acquire a budget to develop their respective countries is through taxes. These taxes will provide funding for employee income and the economy. One of the most popular ticketing systems is Jira ticketing system Jira, a proprietary system launched in 2002. The researchers conducted research aiming to determine the effectiveness of Jira as a ticketing system despite its limited features. The researchers used a descriptive method to analyze the pros and cons of this ticketing System. It is concluded that this Jira Ticketing system is helpful for both support groups and internal members of the company as they track all the incidents and request tickets for their clients despite the limited features of the Jira ticketing system. Jose Rodel Clapano(2022). The Metro Manila Council will prioritize the implementation of a unified ticketing system in the National Capital Region to harmonize the payment of fines over traffic violations committed by motorists, newly installed MMC president, and San Juan Mayor Francis Zamora announced yesterday. Zamora believed that the single ticketing System would help ease traffic congestion in Metro Manila. The MMC, the policy-making body of the

Metropolitan Manila Development Authority (MMDA), comprises 17 mayors in the region. Under the unified ticketing scheme, Zamora said the MMDA and Land Transportation Office would tag the digital records of erring motorists to ensure they could not renew their licenses. Violators may pay their fines online through payment centers.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective is to provide an E-ticket mo: web-based assessor ticketing system for Tagudin Municipality. Specifically, to determine the current process of ticketing in the municipality of Tagudin, Ilocos Sur; to identify the features that are integrated into the System; and to assess the level of acceptability of the suggested System.

III. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study covered the assessor's office of Tagudin Municipality transaction process of receiving, preparing, verifying, and approving transactions. The System only allows four user levels: Staff 1, 2, 3 and the head assessor.

However, the system did not integrate transaction form. Instead, the System focused on queuing the transaction ticket. It will only be used by the staff, can only be used in the assessor's office of LGU Tagudin and requires an internet connection.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The study utilized descriptive developmental type of research to analyze the pros and cons of this ticketing System. Rapid Application Development (RAD) Model by Conrad, Misenar, and Feldman (2012) is utilized as guide to develop the e-ticketing system.

Flow Chart 1: Rapid Application Model

V. FINDINGS

The researchers utilized purposive sampling that helped them determine the respondents' distribution, involving the Administrator and Staff in the municipality of Tagudin and IT expert in Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College Tagudin Campus.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the selected respondents to participate in the acceptability of the proposed system. The study involved the participation of four respondents, namely the employees of the Tagudin municipality, one Administrator, and eight staff.

Table 1: Distribution Of Respondents

Respondents	N
Administrator	1
Staff	8
IT Expert	1
Total:	10

Along objective number 1, the researchers conducted an interview to determine the current process of the ticketing in the assessor’s office. Along objective number 3, the researchers adopted Website Analysis and Measurement Inventory (WAMMI) survey instrument. WAMMI has 20 items in the questionnaire that uses the 5-point scale. Some of the statements are positive, and others have negative (Nur Sukinah Aziz et al, 2021). Frequency count and mean were utilized to analyze the gathered data.

The process of conducting the E-Ticket mo web-based assessor ticketing system of Tagudin municipality was determined through an interview with the head assessor of the assessor's office. Collecting data, including transaction information, is gathered from the assessor's office. The current process of the assessor's office involves the staff manually tracking the status of the transactions, which is time-consuming to find the transaction details, such as the date and name of the recipient. With the System, they can save time than the usual process.

The developed System has the core functionalities of receiving, preparing, verifying, and approving transactions. The system consists of three (4) user levels staff one and two will receive transactions, Staff two will prepare transactions, Staff 3 will verify transactions, and the head assessor will approve transactions. This will be further discussed in the plates. Additionally, the system has certain handy features that supplement the system's main functionalities, such as queuing and tracking transactions. The following hardware and software applications are required for the development of the system: Software Requirements: Internet browser, the Internet, desktop or laptop, and Smartphone. Hardware Requirements: CPU: Intel Dual Core or higher processor, Memory: 512 MB to1 GB memory of ram,1 GB of available disk space.

Below are the major plates of the developed system.

Fig. 1: Admin Panel Dashboard

The fig 1 Shows the admin dashboard panel. It contains buttons to navigate the admin panel, such as Dashboard, View all Transactions, Current Transactions, and Logout.

The fig 2 shows the list of the client's transactions staff one or staff two received and its current status, this section is visible to all users.

The fig 3 shows the transaction progress, the date of when, and who received, prepared, verified, and approved the transaction.

The fig 4 shows the verified transactions ready to approve it also shows approved transactions.

The fig 5 shows the add client transactions where staffs adds/receive client transaction.

Fig. 2: List Of All Transactions

Fig. 3: List Of All Transactions

Fig. 4: Client Transactions

Fig. 5: Add Client Transactions

In the evaluation of acceptability, the highest mean rating is 4.5, describe as very highly acceptable which implies that the developed e ticketing system catch the interest of the user since it has simple procedures in using the system. The lowest mean rating is 3.1 which implies that the users do not agree that the users still need introductory explanations to use the systems.

Overall, the mean rating is 4.04 describe as “Highly Acceptable”. This implies that the respondents perceived that the E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality was acceptable because of simplicity, easy to use and meets the user requirements. As a result, the E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality is acceptable.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the conclusions were stated as follows:

- With the existing process of ticketing at the assessor's office of Tagudin municipality, it is time-consuming to queue and track transactions manually. Therefore, there is a need to develop the E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality.
- The result of the interview was used to determine the features of the developed E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality. Therefore, all parts were integrated into the developed System.
- The developed E-Ticket Mo: Web-Based Assessor Ticketing System of Tagudin Municipality gets an overall acceptance rating of 4.04 "Highly Acceptable" which implies that the developed System is indeed Acceptable to improve the existing process of receiving, preparing, verifying, and approving transactions in the assessor's office of Tagudin.

VII. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the researchers therefore recommend the following:

- The developed System for the assessor's office of Municipality of Tagudin should be adopted and utilized.
- The municipality should consider availing better web hosting plan to maintain running the developed System.
- The users should undergo training on how to use the developed system properly.

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